

Review article

Machine learning and AI-driven digital twins in manufacturing of advanced metal alloys and compounds: A review

Mohsen Soori^{a,*}, Behrooz Arezoo^b^a Department of Mechanical Engineering, Istanbul Aydin University, Istanbul, Turkey^b CAD/CAPP/CAM Research Center, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Amirkabir University of Technology (Tehran Polytechnic), 424 Hafez Avenue, Tehran 15875-4413, Iran

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ABSTRACT

The advancements in manufacturing have been now revolutionized by implementation of machine learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches along with the Digital Twins (DTs). Manufacturing of alloys and compounds have been developed by applying ML and AI-driven DTs in order to provide intelligent monitoring, predictive maintenance and data processing systems during alloy manufacturing. As a result, information regarding microstructural analysis, structure-processing-property relation and effective approaches for optimal defect reduction can be obtained using the ML and AI-driven DTs during alloy manufacturing. Moreover, predictive modeling approaches for material properties, big data analysis, real-time process monitoring, online control approaches, optimized alloy production can be achieved by implementation of the ML and AI-driven DTs during alloy manufacturing. This review study analyzed novel advancements of ML and AI-based DTs applications in manufacturing of advanced metal alloys and compounds by considering and discussing recent achievement from research works. So, the applications and challenges of ML and AI-driven DTs during alloy manufacturing are discussed in the study in order to reduce processing costs, increase quality of produced alloys, optimize alloy production and enhance performance of produced alloys during working conditions. In order to provide guidelines for the future research works, novel ideas such as explainable AI models, combined AI and ML models in alloy manufacturing are also presented and discussed in the study. Furthermore, by presenting guidelines in the study to reduce waste materials and minimize power consumption during alloy production, a substantial development of alloy manufacturing can be achieved. Thus, the discussion of ML and AI-driven DTs during alloy manufacturing can provide guidelines for researchers in order to increase sustainability and productivity during manufacturing process of alloys and compounds.

1. Introduction

Manufacturing procedures have been completely integrated by Industry 4.0, which applied advanced technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in processes of part production. Digital Twins (DTs), has grown into a powerful tool in the era of Industry 4.0 by providing real-time monitoring, optimization, and simulation of manufacturing processes [1]. In order to simulate and analyze the real words in virtual environments, DTs as virtual representations of real-world systems are applied to the advanced manufacturing [2].

The industrial scene has changed dramatically due to integration of DT technologies by using the ML and AI, especially in manufacturing

processes of sophisticated alloys and compounds [3]. Integration of DT by the ML and AI provides unprecedented insights and predictive capabilities, particularly in the complex sector of creating complex metals and chemicals. [4]. By applying ML and AI in DTs technologies, predictive and adaptive capabilities can be obtained which can enhance performances of DTs in complex manufacturing environments [5]. In order to increase accuracy as well as adaptability of metal alloy compound manufacturing in advanced industries, AI-driven DTs are being applied [6]. Therefore, productivity as well as quality of produced parts can be enhanced by applying AI-driven DTs in terms of predicting material behaviors and optimizing manufacturing parameters [7].

The process of producing advanced alloys and compounds is a complex process which requires stringent control over several variables

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: Mohsensoori@aydin.edu.tr, Mohsen.soori@gmail.com (M. Soori), arezoo@aut.ac.ir (B. Arezoo).<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nxmte.2026.102623>

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such as temperature, pressure, composition and microstructural developments [8]. Used Superalloys in several high-performance applications such as aerospace, energy and biomedical sectors require expertise and precision during their manufacturing process [9]. The process of monitoring and optimizing conventional ways of manufacturing is a lengthy, resource-consuming, and trial-and-error process. The implementation of ML and AI-based DTs is redefining companies by delivering predictive analytics for improvements to processes which can be considered as a crucial for generating excellence with low operating costs [10]. Also, challenges of production process can be identified and resolved using the capabilities of ML and AI based DTs technologies by utilizing smart algorithms for predicting, anomaly identification, and optimizing production processes [11]. ML and AI based DTs can analyze data in real time in order to provide proactive decision-making, smart quality control and waste minimization during manufacturing process. Operation of a process DT in a real-time diagnostic control capacity is shown in the Fig. 1 [12].

Applications of AI-enhanced DTs in the processing of alloys manufacturing are studied in different research works. Digital twins have been employed to develop models for additive processing of nickel-based superalloys by allowing control of the microstructure and mechanical properties at a microscale level [13]. Similarly, AI-based digital twins have been utilized in order to optimize heat treatment cycles of aerospace titanium alloys with the objective of decreasing energy requirements [14].

Furthermore, several case studies are available that highlight the capability of optimization procedures by applying AI in alloy manufacturing techniques. For example, DTs were used in order to optimize the additive processing of titanium alloy manufacturing to obtain optimal microstructure and desired mechanical properties [15]. Moreover, AI models were used to optimize heat treatment processes of superalloys during manufacturing of superalloys to develop optimal creep properties and minimize production variability [16].

Regarding alloy and compound production, various AI-based DT models have been proposed by offering unique advantages during modelling process. Supervised learning methods using support vector machines and artificial neural networks based on past process data, are very accurate methods in terms of predicting mechanical properties and microstructure development [17]. Reinforcement learning methods are used in optimizing processes through simulated environments in order to provide suitable models for difficult nonlinear industrial problems [18]. Unsupervised learning methods can also be applied in developing robustness through significant assistance in diagnostics and anomalies cases [19]. Moreover, combined approach modelling procedures are

consist of AI-based ML and physics-based modeling during alloy manufacturing processes. It can significantly improve accuracy of prediction and data analysis during alloy manufacturing modelling [20].

However, application of AI-based DTs has different challenges and difficulties within different industries. Though having great potential, there remain many challenges in adapting AI-based process optimization for alloy production [7]. These include computational complexity involved with model formulations for large-scale production processes, requirements for representative and high-quality data, and adapting AI tools with existing manufacturing infrastructure [21]. The need for a large amount of labeled data which are sometimes hard to acquire within practical processes of actual alloys can limit supervised learning models [22]. Moreover, the effectiveness and potential applicability of reinforcement learning models can be severely hampered by limitations of training time due to dynamic processes of industrial environments [18]. Generative models such as GANs can also face a lack of realism in physical environments due to limitations of strong integration with domain knowledge. So, the limitations can minimize developed models capabilities to mimic material environments during manufacturing process of alloys [23]. Also, the traditional set of metrics is used to evaluate different learning model performances on diverse tasks such as real-time control. As a result, process and prediction tasks are inadequate in terms of evaluation of developed model performances [24].

The applications of ML and AI-driven DTs in manufacturing of advanced metal alloys and compounds is summarized in the Table 1.

The application of DTs through ML and AI can integrate the alloy production process to provide intelligent and environmentally conscious manufacturing systems in order to improve productivity in component production. This paper provides novel review paper regarding the previous studies, which had largely focused on the isolated use of AI-based DTs and instead aims at their integrated implementation by covering the shortcomings in predictive analytical capabilities, microstructural development and control. Through the analysis and review of the existing literature on the application of AI for improving the effectiveness of DTs in Industry 4.0, the paper introduces novel ideas and approaches related to manufacturing process of advanced alloys and compositions. The aim of the study is presenting a detailed assessment of DTs through ML and AI application in manufacturing of complex alloys and compounds. Furthermore, the paper describes recent advancements and trends, raises relevant issues, and provides a guideline for future studies. The novel ideas for future research work directions such as explainable AI models, combined AI and ML models in alloy manufacturing are also presented and discussed in the study in order to provide guidelines for the future research works. As a result, the paper

Fig. 1. Using a process DT in a diagnostic control capacity in real time [12].

Table 1
The applications of ML and AI-driven DTs in manufacturing of advanced metal alloys and compounds.

Method/Technique	Applications	Advantages	Disadvantages and Limitations	Quantitative/Case Outcomes
Supervised Learning such as, Neural Networks, SVM, RF.	Process prediction, microstructure-property modeling	High prediction accuracy for structured datasets; well-established	Requires labeled datasets; poor generalization to unseen data	High accuracy in predicting hardness & tensile strength in titanium alloys [25]
Unsupervised Learning such as, PCA, Clustering)	Anomaly detection, pattern discovery	No labeling required; good for exploratory analysis	Difficult to validate results; sensitive to noise	Used to detect real-time anomalies in rolling processes [26]
Reinforcement Learning (RL)	Process optimization such as, heat treatment, laser paths	Adaptive; effective for non-linear, sequential tasks	High computational cost; long training times	Improved process efficiency in additive manufacturing applications [27]
Transfer Learning	Cross-domain adaptation such as, from steel to nickel alloys	Reduces training cost; allows knowledge reuse	Domain mismatch risks; requires fine-tuning	Reduced model training time for similar alloy systems
Generative Models (GANs, VAEs)	Virtual experiments, synthetic microstructure generation	Supports data augmentation; enables exploration of unseen scenarios	Often lacks interpretability; prone to instability during training	Generated microstructure data closely matched experimental data in porosity predictions [28]
Explainable AI such as, SHAP, LIME	Decision support and model transparency	Enhances trust and interpretability	Computational overhead; limited support in complex models	Improved interpretability of neural models used for alloy property prediction [29]

contributes towards process optimization, performance prediction, and manufacturing monitoring in advanced metal alloys and metal composition manufacturing processes.

2. Digital twin applications in alloy manufacturing

DTs in premium alloy technology provide an approach that imposes simulations and optimizations of processes such as casting, heat treatment and testing of alloys [30]. By leveraging historical and real-time data DTs can provide:

1. Predict Process Outcomes: The ML model incorporated in the DTs technique can be applied in order to predict the changes in the microstructure, phases and mechanical properties of produced alloys regarding the process parameters during manufacturing procedures [31].

Workflow of a DT in additive technologies is shown in the Fig. 2 [32].

2. Optimized Manufacturing Parameters: Different parameters such as temperature, cooling rates and pressure can be optimized in order to increase performance during manufacturing processes of alloys. AI algorithms enable real-time adjustments in order to optimize parameters such as, and, ensuring uniform quality and reducing defects [33].

3. Failure Detection and Mitigation: In order to minimize wastes and downtime during manufacturing processes of different alloys, online monitoring can be applied [34].
4. Accelerate Development Cycles: Using performed simulations and analyses in virtual environment, the demand of physical tests can be decreased. The digital twin-based virtual prototyping can eliminate the need for physical testing of prototypes due to accurate simulation and analysis in virtual environments [7].

Standard mechanical sample high-throughput casting models using DT application is shown in the Fig. 3 [30].

3. Data-Driven modeling in DTs for alloy manufacturing

Advanced metal and compound manufacturing processes involve nonlinear multi-physics phenomena such as solidification and phase transformations. However, there are several challenges by applying the traditional physics-driven models during simulation process [35]. Deep learning methods as well as Gaussian Process Regression models can provide effective tools in simulating these phenomena by applying experimental and simulation data. For example, ML algorithms have been used in order to accurately predict phase stability in multi-component alloy systems in terms of bypassing the need for exhaustive thermodynamic calculations [36]. Similarly, AI-driven DTs can integrate real-time sensor data from production lines in order to

Fig. 2. DT workflow in additive technologies [32].

Fig. 3. Standard mechanical sample high-throughput casting models using DT applications [30].

dynamically update developed models in terms of ensuring high fidelity between the virtual and physical systems [37]. Applications of Data-Driven Modeling in DTs for alloy manufacturing can be presented as:

- **Material Design and Optimization:** The data-driven model can predict the effects of alloying elements and the variables of the process on the final properties of the materials. As a result, optimized designing procedures can be obtained using data-driven models in alloy manufacturing [38].
- **Process Control and Optimization:** With the combination of real-time information and ML algorithms, adaptive control processes can now be developed specifically for alloy manufacturing, thereby ensuring that the alloy properties meet the specified criteria while minimizing waste and energy usage [39].
- **Predictive Maintenance:** Predictive models could be utilized for predicting failures and deviations in the equipment in order to provide smart predictive maintenance during alloy manufacturing. These processes are even more essential during accurate manufacturing of alloys in order to minimize downtimes and costs of part production [40].

Using process-induced thermal histories to correlate and forecast mechanical characteristics in metal additive manufacturing through the application of a mechanistic data-driven framework is shown in the Fig. 4 [41].

Fig. 5 illustrates application of deep-learning-enhanced DTs for real-time mechanical interaction of complex composite structures [42].

In conclusion, to improve the production rate of advanced alloys and compounds, integrated procedures as data-driven models based on the concept of digital twins can be applied [30,43]. The integration of AI and ML technologies into alloys production systems can be used to reduce the production cost and predict the behavior of materials for a smoother and sustainable production process [44].

4. Machine learning techniques in digital twins for alloy manufacturing

The application of methods based on ML in DTs has significantly changed the production process of complex alloys and compounds [30]. By enabling the real-time processing, predicting, and optimizing data, ML improves both the productivity and quality through the intersection of the digital and physical domains. The following outlines introduce the key methods of DTs application in alloy manufacturing procedures.

1. **Supervised Learning for Process Prediction and Control:** DTs employs supervised ML algorithms like Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Random Forests and Neural Networks in order to predict the results of the processes being managed and control the process variables [45]. Process parameters such as pressure, temperature and chemical composition are used to train the developed ML algorithms in terms of process properties prediction including the microstructural development, hardness and tensile strength [46]. For instance, neural net model might be used to predict the effects of the variation of cooling rate on the grain structure of an alloy in order to correctly control the alloy manufacturing process [47].
2. **Unsupervised Learning for Anomaly Detection:** Unsupervised machine learning approaches, such as clustering and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), play a critical role in the aspect of anomaly detection in the sense that they help in the recognition of anomalies within the real-time data from the process [48]. system has the ability to identify patterns of anomalies and deviations within the chemical composition that might have an effect on the quality of the end product. Therefore, the data can be applied by the digital twin for correction during the process of alloy manufacturing [49].
3. **Reinforcement Learning for Process Optimization:** In order to optimize production processes within the DT models, Reinforcement Learning (RL) has been applied in different applications [50]. Within this framework, an RL agent interacts with a DT-based environment

Fig. 4. Using process-induced thermal histories to correlate and forecast mechanical characteristics in metal additive manufacturing through the application of a mechanistic data-driven framework [41].

Fig. 5. Application of Deep-learning-enhanced DTs for real-time mechanical interaction of complex composite structures [42].

to learn policies that improve production efficiency and minimize waste. For instance, RL techniques can be utilized to optimize heat treatment processes during manufacturing process. The procedure is implemented in order to obtain optimal energy efficiency during

alloy production and provide desired mechanical properties of produced alloys [51]. These adaptable properties of RL models are suitable for modification of alloy production with nonlinear dynamics processes [27].

4. **Transfer Learning for Cross-Domain Adaptation:** Transfer learning can be applied to train and modify generated model for different manufacturing domain in terms of reducing the need for extensive re-training process and minimizing computational time [52]. This is very useful in the DT environment as the method has common dynamics to be applicable to similar alloys [76]. For example, A trained model for steel alloy production can be modified and applied to the production of titanium alloys because both involve common knowledge related to metallurgy [53].
5. **Generative Models for Virtual Experimentation:** These generative models, such as variational autoencoders (VAEs) and generative adversarial networks (GANs), are used in digital twins (DTs) for virtual experimentations [54]. The ability to generate believable process conditions and alloy compositions enables explorations into novel alloys as well as novel methods for alloy production [55]. For instance, a microstructure generated using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) based on different compositions of alloys can be used in order to predict the mechanical properties of produced alloy without necessarily undertaking experimental processes [56].
6. **Explainable AI for Decision Support:** Explainable AI techniques enhance the interpretability of ML models used in DTs in order to provide accurate and reliable predictions and recommendations during alloy manufacturing [57]. For example, methods that help to interpret correlations between input and output variables can be presented as SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) and LIME (Local Interpretable Explanation) Explanation which can help to promote trustworthiness between ML-Based processes and alloy development [58]. Thus, in order to provide reliable decision-making during alloy manufacturing, modern and transparent AI strategies such as SHAP and LIME to verify the prediction and decision results [59]. So, by using the methods, engineers are able to find the most important variables which has a massive impact on outcome predictions in order to validate results and increase accuracy of decision support systems [60]. For instance, predictions involving SHAP can be applied to validate defect development influenced by cooling rates and composition, while LIME explains localized predictions can be used to alloy development predictions involving microstructural development. These validate interpretability within alloy development to verify processes, improve trust between developers and

Fig. 6. Optimized printed components with enhanced ML algorithm and data of historical process [64].

ensure compliance with regulation [61]. Patterns in data can be obtained using ML algorithms and AI models are providing optimization and decision-making during alloy manufacturing process [62]. Also, ML algorithms can be applied to identify anomalies and make predictions in DTs, while AI encompasses all these capabilities in addition to adaptive decision-making in order to generate intelligent and self-optimizing systems [63].

Fig. 6 displays superior printed components that use enhanced ML algorithm and data of historical process [64].

As a result, ML and generative models of digital twins can provide accurate simulation and analysis of production process data in terms of performance enhancement of alloy manufacturing. Thus, product quality enhancement, minimization of material waste and optimized process parameters are achieved by applying ML and digital twin during alloy manufacturing [65]. Thus, future research works can focus on incorporating real-time learning models to enhance the efficiency of ML-based Digital Twins in producing alloys [66].

5. Predictive maintenance of superalloy manufacturing using ML and AI-enabled DTs

Availability of reliable equipment is needed during the production processes for the production of superalloys to achieve the desired goal. Unplanned stoppage time related to the failure of critical equipment like the rolling mill, forging press and furnace may cause delays in the supply chain during the manufacturing plant. The loss of potential income that can be correlated to this breakdown might be significant [67]. Additionally, the usage of superalloys is often associated with high-performance products in the aerospace industry, energy industry, or the automotive industry. High accuracy is required in the manufacturing processes associated with such industries [68]. However, the incorporation of DTs using ML and AI capabilities has been revolutionary in the predictive maintenance and optimization associated with the manufacturing processes of superalloys [4]. Additionally, DTs with ML capabilities can predict potential breakdowns during the manufacturing process in order to minimize downtime of alloy production [69]. The predictive maintenance of superalloy manufacturing using ML and AI-enabled DTs can provide:

1. **Real-Time Condition Monitoring:** By examining the characteristics of vibration, temperature, and sound, ML models can identify anomalies that predict mechanical breakdowns [70]. This is due to the fact that flaws in the manufacturing of complicated alloys can negatively impact both the precision casting and powder bed fusion processes during additive manufacturing processes [71]. AI algorithms developed by DTs can examine sensor data in order to predict any issues before they arise which can reduce downtime and boost productivity of part manufacturing [10].
2. **Enhancing Maintenance with AI-Driven Insights:** In order to provide accurate date during the maintenance procedures, AI algorithms based on ML models are used to analyze data generated by DTs [50]. These insights allow operators to schedule maintenance proactively, optimizing production schedules and reducing unplanned downtimes [72]. AI-driven PdM also help in the allocation of resources which parts are to be fixed immediately and which parts are left functional. So, the operational expenses can be decreased in order to enhance the life of costly equipment during working operations [73].
3. **Failure Pattern Recognition using ML:** Operating characteristics and maintenance information combine well with the capabilities of AI, allowing diagnosis related to the estimation of the RUL of a component. Under PdM, several techniques, such as artificial neural networks, SVMs, and decision trees under ML, find extensive applications [74]. For example, to treat superalloys for production purposes, temporal relationships are successfully encoded through

RNNs and LSTMs in order to provide reliable and early fault detection system for furnaces, rollers and machining devices [75].

4. **Dynamic Maintenance Scheduling:** With predictive analysis, industries are able to shift from time-related approaches to condition-related approaches in terms of maintenance scheduling. The procedure can help to maximize machine life in order to increase performance of alloy manufacturing. Digital Twins are models that simulate real-world objects and processes. Digital Twins are dynamic models which can simulate real-world observation of manufacturing processes [76]. During manufacturing of superalloy, digital twins can simulate and predict possible failures by using information assembled from both sensors and data analysis in order to increase accuracy and reliability of simulation process. As a result, DTs can provide accurate and reliable equipment performance analysis and process stability in order to predict anomalies and prevent expensive downtimes during alloy manufacturing [77].

As a result, unplanned downtime, and maintenance process can be minimized in order to enhance manufacturing quality for superalloys manufacturing. So, production efficiency, reliability and quality can be achieved by using real-time information and data analytics during alloy manufacturing. But, there are challenges faced by predictive maintenance in superalloy manufacturing processes [78]. Adverse environments, such as high temperatures as well as pressure can affect to the accuracy of sensors, leading to inaccuracies in the generation of data. Moreover, in predictive maintenance of superalloy manufacturing, it is required to produce high-quality data for accurate model development due to complexity of process [79]. Incorporation of existing systems with modern platforms based on AI for DTs is another issue due to demand of large amount of financial resources and technical knowledge [80].

In summary, PdM powered by ML and AI-driven DTs offers a promising pathway to enhance reliability and efficiency of superalloy manufacturing processes [81]. Therefore, PdM is expected to become a key component of contemporary sophisticated alloy and compound production processes as a result of continuous technical improvements by using ML and AI-enabled DTs. [82].

6. Real-time process monitoring and control of alloy manufacturing

In order to manufacture high-performance alloys, it becomes important to control the various variables involved in the process, which include temperature, pressure, cooling rate and chemical composition. The integration of ML an AI-based DTs is transforming the manufacturing process, which has the capability of real-time monitoring and controlling of alloy manufacturing process. If any variation occurs in the production parameters, it would result in the production of alloys, which would be difficult and challenging to identify by using conventional methods. Real-time data acquisition and analysis can be enabled by the application of DTs, which can access data related to the industrial processes through the applications of IoTs technologies. In particular, during the process of alloy production, sensors can monitor critical data such as temperature gradients, phase transformations and microstructure of manufactured alloys. AI-Based Image processing algorithms can also evaluate data on surface defects and crystal structures during casting and rolling processes [83]. Furthermore, machine vision systems equipped with AI technology and smart sensors can analyze surface defects and grain structure during casting as well as rolling processes [84]. Consequently, digital twins boosted by AI technology can provide an advanced real-time monitoring and modification process during the production of alloys. Applications of AI-enhanced DTs in Real-time process monitoring and control of alloy manufacturing can be presented as,

1. **Predictive Process Control:** In order to predict manufacturing process outcomes at any instance in time with real-time data inputs, neural networks and Gaussian process regression as ML algorithms can be used [39]. As a result, DTs can predict any deviation in the process before defects are created by training these models on historical and experimental data [84]. For instance, the AI-driven Predictive models can forecast the cooling rates impacts to alloy phases. As a result, the data can provide guidelines for operators with knowledge about changing process parameters and manufacturing required material qualities in order to analyze and modify the alloy production process parameters [85].
2. **Closed-loop Feedback Systems:** closed-loop feedback systems can be created by digital twins in order to provide consistency within alloy production. Closed-loop feedback systems utilize real-time knowledge in order to automatically implement modification due to any changes by processes parameters [80]. For instance, during the production of advanced alloys through AM, DTs are able to detect overheating due to laser power as well as scan rates in real time in order to avoid porosity and cracks in the produced parts. So, the system can reduce waste and improves general productivity of alloy manufacturing [86].
3. **Benefits for Alloy Manufacturing:** Application of real-time process monitoring and control through DTs offers several advantages:
 - **Improved Quality Control:** The reliability of the model can be affected by noisy, incomplete, or mismatched data obtained from sensors in harsh environments during high-speed processes such as rolling as well as casting processes [87]. In order to increase confidence level in predictions procedures, uncertainty quantification methods such as ensemble learning, Bayesian analysis, and probabilistic models can be employed. Better anomaly detection leads to optimal material properties with lesser volume of computational works [88].
 - **DTs in minimizations of uncertainty during real-time predictions:** The integration of sensor fusion and Kalman filters into the structure of DTs can help in the minimization of uncertainty generated in the form of disparate data streams [89]. During real-time predictions using DTs, adaptive control methods as well as feedback process can be applied in order to minimize uncertainties of measured parameters during alloys manufacturing such as temperature, gradients and phase transformations [90]. So, minimization of uncertainty measures during production of advanced alloys can be obtained using applications of DTs and ML algorithms in order to increase accuracy of real time monitoring [91].
 - **Reduced Downtime:** Reliable equipment failure and process problem detection and prediction systems minimize downtime.
 - **Sustainability:** material waste and energy consumption can be minimized by using optimized resource and energy usage in terms of achieving sustainable manufacturing goals [92].

In summary, the use of AI-based DTs for a real-time process monitoring and control function can integrate the process of alloy production in order to increase sustainability and productivity of alloy manufacturing.

7. Process optimization of superalloy manufacturing

Complex processes such as melting, casting, hot working and heat treatment are used during the production of of manufactured superalloys. It is important to apply accurate control during the production process to achieve the desired properties [93]. Optimization of the processes used in the production of advanced alloys is a fundamental aspect that affects the properties and costs associated with the production. For example, optimization procedures such as genetic algorithms and reinforcement learning can be applied in order to achieve desired microstructures and mechanical properties for WLEDs [94]. Optimized

DTs for AI have the prospective capability to close porosities and raise yield strength during AM process for superalloys [95]. Such technologies allow monitoring, controlling, and prediction of manufactured alloy properties in terms of alloy manufacturing integration. AI-driven DTs enhance process optimization through:

1. **Data-Driven Process Insights:** AI-based DTs utilize a big data of process parameters and material properties based on sensors which are obtained from alloy manufacturing process, simulations and experimental works [69]. ML-based techniques are utilized to analyze and discover hidden patterns that cannot easily be detected with help of the common process. For example, a supervised machine-based learning technique can be used in order to predict the impact of process variables such as temperature, cooling rate and pressure on the microstructural and mechanical properties of produced alloys. Moreover, unsupervised machine-based learning techniques can be used in identifying hidden patterns and properties during alloy manufacturing [96].
2. **Predictive Process Control:** One of the most influential uses of AI in improving processes is predictive process control. DTs are capable of using predictive ML models for understanding real-time sensor information in terms of providing predictive control and modifications [97]. For example, in a casting or heat treatment procedure, predictive models using AI can identify any defects in terms of porosity and undesirable grain structures to modify process parameters and overcome such difficulties. As a result, manufacturing processes of alloys can be integrated to increase performances of produced alloys [98].
3. **Optimization Algorithms for Parameter Tuning:** Advanced optimization techniques such as Genetic Algorithms, Particle Swarm Optimization and Bayesian Optimization are presently being used in optimization of alloy production processes [99]. Such algorithms are able to efficiently search in a high-dimensional space for optimal parameters in order to choose the optimized parameters which can offer desired properties in produced alloys. Such algorithms are able to perform virtual experiments by incorporating decision trees in order to minimize downtime and cost in trial and error procedures [100].
4. **Multi-Objective Optimization:** The production of alloys can involve processes that require satisfying multiple conflicting criteria concurrently, such as minimizing strength and weight at the same time. For optimizing such problems, multi-object optimization methods supported by ML algorithms can be applied. To explore the various parameters of the manufacturing process related to the achievement of the Pareto optimum points, decision trees can introduce a simulation platform [101].
5. **Autonomous Process Optimization:** the final aim of AI and DTs integration has been considered as the optimization of autonomous processes. Reinforcement learning (RL) has proven to be an effective technique during manufacturing process of alloys. Reinforcement learning agents have interacted with virtual environments in the field of DTs in order to gain experience through the process of constant improvement by trials and errors procedures [102]. RL-driven system can optimize furnace temperatures and cooling profiles by monitoring variations in raw material qualities and process conditions without human intervention in order to increase accuracy and reliability of manufacturing process [103].
6. **Process Parameter Optimization:** These tools assist in determining the best possible value for the variables in the process concerning the input mapping, which may include factors such as temperature, pressure, rate of cooling and outputs such as grain, strength, and durability. This is enormously beneficial to the development stage where experimentation and guessing are now reduced.
7. **Real-Time Process Control:** Through the monitoring of the values of the process variables, the DTs make adjustments to the process

parameters in order to attain optimal process conditions and qualitative production of the parts [104].

8. Defect Prediction and Prevention: The AI algorithms can be applied in order to predict defects like porosity, cracks and segregation during alloy manufacturing process. So, the procedure can provide the corrective actions for manufacturing process by using defect prediction data in order to enhance quality of produced alloys.

Application of DT in analysis and optimization of additive manufacturing is shown in the Fig. 7 [105].

8. Real-Time decision support and adaptive control of superalloy manufacturing

One of the most attractive areas of AI-related applications in DTs is in real-time decision support systems and adaptive controls. Highly alloyed systems like high-entropy alloys demand strict controls over composition and processes [106]. The AI-enabled DTs would also have the ability to adaptively modify conditions such as temperature, pressure, and cooling rates, depending upon the variations that emerge during the process of manufacturing. To achieve near-instantaneous predictions of material responses to differing conditions, neural network models could be applied [107]. It is considered as an important tool during designing and development of alloys due to demand of examination of a vast number of variants [7]. As a result, the analyzed data are considered as important dataset during alloy and compound manufacturing process in order to increase accuracy of real-time decision support and adaptive control of superalloy manufacturing [36,108]. Therefore, models such as reinforcement learning of AI could assist the DTs in terms of gathering data associated with manufacture of alloys. Thus, modified superalloys can be generated regarding the DTs analysis of data in processes of heat treatment of alloy manufacturing [109]. DTs aided by big data for intelligent advanced material design and production is shown in the Fig. 8 [30].

Self-optimization of the production processes as adaptive control systems can be implemented due to continuously monitoring the changes in process conditions and variable environmental impacts. To predict the consequences of different control measures, ML algorithms

can be applied for training procedures by historic and simulated datasets. The advanced ML algorithms can independently make adjustments in the process variables, such as temperature, pressure, and composition in order to ensure the performances of optimal conditions. [110]. Adaptive control systems are also essential part of production of complex molecules in order to pursue favorable chemical composition and microstructure. The procedure is particularly important when dealing with complex multi-step reactions during alloy manufacturing [111]. Application of ML algorithm in real-time process control and in situ defect monitoring during directed energy deposition method of additive manufacturing process is presented in Fig. 9 [112].

9. Challenges and opportunities

Although the potential of AI-based digital twins in alloy manufacturing is enormous, there are still some challenges that need to be solved. The generation of efficient ML models in alloy manufacturing is based on accurate and high-quality of production parameter data, which is always with challenges and difficulties [113]. Explainable AI techniques can be used in order to provide efficient implementation of alloy manufacturing integration [114]. There are several challenges involved in the implementation of AI-based DTs for the manufacturing of alloys which can be presented as:

- Data Availability and Quality: The use of high-fidelity data is a necessary requirement for the developer to create an accurate model of ML. However, working with high-fidelity data consumes a considerable amount of time. The management of noisy, inadequate and time-varying sensor data associated with extreme production settings like high temperatures, vibrations and corrosive environments that often occur during alloy production are different challenges of alloy manufacturing [115]. So, proper implementation of ML and AI-driven DTs in the production of alloys relies to the big data analysis [116]. These inconsistencies could lead to improper model development and prediction errors. Also, the lack of a standardized structure for the diverse array of sensors and systems involved creates a challenge of consolidating the data and generalization of the model [117]. For the purposes of ensuring the ability of

Fig. 7. Application of DT in analysis and optimization of additive manufacturing [105].

Fig. 8. DTs aided by big data for intelligent advanced material design and production [30].

Fig. 9. Application of ML algorithm in real-time process control and in situ defect monitoring during directed energy deposition method of additive manufacturing process [112].

the ML model for proper interaction and reusability across all systems involved, standardization of approaches for all data collection and formats should be applied. The integration of diverse data from multiple sources such as spectrometer equipment, production data and thermographic sensors is another challenging task that demands a sophisticated degree of harmonization to mitigate contradictions [118]. Hence, model development for proper processing or real-time control and TL features within the AI-driven DTs remain directly impacted [90]. Thus, in order to provide reliable ML algorithm during alloy production, advanced preprocessing techniques, proper data imputation techniques, variant calibration techniques and strict guidelines on preconceived schemas should be implemented [119].

- Integration with Legacy Systems: Due to the limitations of traditional techniques and complexities of alloy production technology, it is difficult and challenging to apply the legacy systems to traditional systems. Thus, the current DT frameworks are inapplicable to the traditional systems due to limitations of adapting to the advanced methods [120].
- Computational Demands: Real-time simulation of complex physical phenomena is a highly computationally intensive task, especially when ML models need to be incorporated. As a result, volume of

commotional work during alloy manufacturing integration is increased due to real-time data analysis procedures.

The challenges of AI-based digital twins in alloy manufacturing are due to important alloy manufacturing factors and parameters such as high temperatures and pressure which can impact to the data quality of sensors and hence provide erroneous information [121]. In addition, there is a need for quality data in the training of the models considering the nature of the processes involved in the creation of the superalloys. The integration of legacy systems with modern AI-driven DTs is another challenge which may require significant financial investments.

10. Conclusion

The manufacturing processes of advanced alloys and compounds is modified by using ML and AI-powered DTs. These processes allow for a degree of precision, flexibility, and optimization that was not possible before in design and processing techniques. The incorporation of ML and AI has introduced a new methodology in order to improve sustainability and reduce wastes. These processes have made possible a fully optimized automation of control processes during the production of advanced

materials. So, optimized alloy properties and waste reduction in manufacturing processes can be achieved by applying ML and AI through DTs during process of alloy production.

However, the use of AI-driven DTs in the manufacture of alloys holds numerous challenges despite the immense possibilities. For effective implementation of AI-driven DTs, there are challenges that need to be considered, which include model interpretability, scalability, and quality of measured data. There are also challenges that include the cost of computation for the real-time simulation that requires the application of advanced ML algorithms. The complexity of the data requires a high level of fidelity and interoperability of various sensors and legacy systems, which can provide challenges of establishing trust in opaque AI models. Moreover, the application of DT frameworks can be hampered by the presence of legacy infrastructure, which requires immense capital expenditure. In this regard, the use of DTs must rely on strict and advanced cybersecurity frameworks. Moreover, cybersecurity standards should be considered in terms of DT technology adoption in order to provide secure and reliable data transaction. So, computer engineers, data scientists and materials scientists should work together in order to provide intelligent, reliable, scalable and sustainable alloy manufacturing systems.

Overall, the synergy between ML, AI, DTs, with data analysis and edge computing can provide excellent devices in simulation, analysis and modification of alloy manufacturing. The producers can be used in optimization of alloy manufacturing in order to provide desired mechanical properties of produced alloys. Moreover, the advanced technologies can be used in competitive marketing to satisfy customer demand and provide sustainable manufacturing process regarding the safety of living environments. As a result, the execution of these latest technologies of combined AI and ML in DTs can increase productivity and sustainability during alloy manufacturing. Finally, the potential for transformation possessed by AI-based DTs is substantial in the manufacturing sector with respect to new alloys and compounds.

11. Future directions

A completely autonomous system which can optimize a process right from beginning to end will be the key to the future of AI-driven DTs in advanced alloy production. This will be further enhanced in the scalability and reliability by integration with Industry 4.0 technologies, such as blockchain for data security and Internet of Things sensors. Moreover, interpretable insights into decision-making processes provided by developments in explainable AI will help to improve user confidence. Future research would include developments in sensor technology, edge analysis, and cloud analysis in attempting to add more relevance of PdM in the superalloy production cycle. The accuracy of prediction can improve with new advancements in ML approaches such as explainable AI. Furthermore, advanced datasets can be provided for training and enhancement of DTs models due to increased capabilities of data collection using IoTs technologies. Fully transformative alloy manufacturing, enabled by ML and AI, has the potential to open the door towards more intelligent, productive, and greener production systems. The future research on applications of ML and AI-driven DTs in the manufacturing of advanced metal alloys and compounds may be suggested as

1. **Hybrid Modeling and Physics-AI Fusion:** A combination of ML techniques and physics-based models is required in hybrid modeling process to accurately model complex material properties during alloy manufacturing. For improving the model predictions with fewer computing costs in decision-making, it is suggested to include ML algorithms in multi-physics modeling in the future.

Importance: Provides predictive validity and possible physical interpretations.

Feasibility: Increasing adoption due to software support such as COMSOL-ML interfaces and available training data.

2. **Application of DTs in decision-making by edge computing and fog computing:** edge computing, fog computing can offer optimal opportunities for precise decision-making processes in alloy production. For example, adaptive changes in additive manufacturing, micro-structural observation of alloys can be achieved by implementation of fog computing and edge computing.

Importance: Crucial for defect mitigation and accuracy control.

Feasibility: Made possible due to advances in AI application development and low-latency networks.

3. **Data Fusion and Multi-Modal Learning:** Data obtained from dissimilar sources, such as thermal images, acoustic signals, microstructure information and IoT sensors can be utilized in order to enhance capability of ML algorithms during simulation of actual production environments.

Importance: Critical for adaptive manufacturing modifications and reliable process monitoring procedures

Feasibility: Feasible with current ML libraries and industrial IoT ecosystems.

4. **Cybersecurity and Trust in DTs:** Due to the enhanced applications of DTs in various industries, proper cybersecurity systems should be developed. The research can be focused on developing an intrusion detection algorithm, blockchain development and secure communication of data in the cloud-based collaborative environment of DTs to increase cybersecurity of DTs.

Importance: Helps protects confidential processes that result in manufactured products

Feasibility: Technologies like blockchain and SSL are mature, requiring contextual adaptation.

5. **Explainable and Transparent AI:** Interpretability is an essential requirement for the industrial application of AI decision support tools. Consequently, the principles of transparency and trust can be optimized using AI technology in smart decision support systems of alloy production.

Importance: Creating Trust and Trustworthy AI-Human Interaction.

Feasibility: Readily available via open-source libraries.

6. **Predictive Maintenance and Lifecycle Management:** novel techniques for productivity and stability enhancement of alloy manufacturing can be presented by applying predictive maintenance coupled with life cycle management procedures.

Importance: Optimizes equipment availability and process capability.

Feasibility: Established through case studies on superalloys.

Forward simulation with prediction of results based on parameters is the central thrust of current research activities. The future research work shall comprise reverse design with a recommendation provided by DT on contents and processing procedures based on the input of required material properties.

Approach: In order to generate potential compositions and process parameters, the application of generative models like GANs or VAEs or transformer-based models that have been trained on large datasets of alloy properties would be employed.

Benefits: Enables faster identification of high-performance alloys required for certain applications such as heat-resistance and corrosion-resistance.

Feasibility: Recent progress in materials informatics and access in order to open databases such as Materials Project and OQMD makes this direction achievable.

The promised gain in prediction precision and support for learning production decisions makes hybrid modeling and real-time control a highly important goal. Due to digital environment development, applications of AI and ML based DTs in different industries are enhanced. The developed systems are applied to the decision-making processes in order to increase capabilities of alloy manufacturing.

Predictive maintenance and security are also important and curtail

issues during the development of AI based DTs in alloy manufacturing. During the study, a strategic roadmap which can guide researchers in the direction of relevant and technically possible areas to shape the future of smart and sustainable production of alloys are presented and discussed. As a result, the presented research directions can enhance effectiveness and scalability of AI-powered DTs within generation of advanced alloys and compounds in order to integrate manufacturing and production processes of alloys.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohsen Soori: Software, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Behrooz Arezoo:** Supervision, Resources, Investigation.

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